

VICTIMOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE AGE OF VICTIMS IN INTENTIONAL HOMICIDE CASES

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Abstract: The article examines the victimological age characteristics of intentional homicide victims. It is noted that the personal and social characteristics of the victim, including age, gender, social status, and marital status, significantly influence the likelihood of becoming a victim of such a crime. Analysis conducted from 2020 to 2024 shows that the majority of victims are socially active and able-bodied individuals aged 25-54, which necessitates the development of targeted preventive measures and protection mechanisms for groups with high victimization risk. The article highlights the importance of a comprehensive victimological study of intentional homicide victims and the significance of developing effective preventive measures.

Keywords: intentional homicide, victim, victimology, age, social vulnerability, prevention

Human life is recognized as the highest and inviolable value in any legal and democratic society. In accordance with Article 25 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the right to life is an inalienable right of every person and is firmly protected by law[1]. Therefore, attempts on human life are considered one of the most serious crimes. However, the current state of crime shows that human life is threatened in various forms. In particular, the crime of intentional homicide remains one of the most pressing and intractable problems as a criminal act that is extremely dangerous to society and has significant social consequences.

Intentional homicide is one of the most serious crimes, the commission of which has a significant impact not only on the victim, but also on their family and social environment[2]. From this point of view, victimological analysis of the victim is important not only for understanding this crime, but also for developing its prevention. In the victimological approach, the victim is considered as a person who has suffered material, moral, or physical damage as a result of the crime. His characteristics, social status, and psychological traits can significantly influence the likelihood of committing premeditated murder.[3]

In-depth study of the causes of these types of crimes, analysis of their socio-economic, psycho-emotional, and cultural causes is one of the important tasks facing modern criminology and victimology.

In particular, one of the main directions of victimological analysis is the study of the personal characteristics, social status, family environment, lifestyle, activity in interpersonal relationships, and the possibility of being exposed to certain dangers of the victim of premeditated murder[4]. After all, a crime manifests itself not only as an act of the criminal, but also as a socio-legal phenomenon that occurs in a certain system of social relations and depends on the indirect or direct participation of the victim.

From the point of view of victimology, the victimological characteristic of a victim of premeditated murder is determined not only by their age, gender, physical condition, or social status, but also by their behavior, place in interpersonal relationships, position in conflicts, and

role in situations preceding the commission of the crime[5]. In-depth analysis of these indicators will make it possible to prevent similar crimes in the future and carry out targeted preventive work with persons with a high degree of victimization.

From this point of view, our scientific research aims to comprehensively study the victimological characteristics of victims of premeditated murder, analyze their role and influence in the process of committing crimes, and thereby develop proposals and recommendations for crime prevention.

The study of the victim of premeditated murder from the point of view of victimology is important for analyzing the factors of the crime's origin, assessing its level of social danger, and determining measures for the prevention of such crimes[6]. By identifying who the victim was as a person, their personal characteristics, social role, and circumstances under which they encountered the crime, it is possible to assess their indirect or direct involvement in the crime.

Demographic characteristics of victims of premeditated murder play a key role in crime analysis. Studies have shown that most often, victims are people of active working age, who have the opportunity to participate in social activity and any relationships, while also being more likely to encounter conflict situations[7]. In terms of gender, there are both men and women among the victims, but in premeditated homicide arising from family relationships, the number of female victims is significantly higher. This situation shows the influence of gender roles and social culture in family conflicts.

The personal and demographic characteristics of the victim, including their age, gender, education, profession, and social status, are important factors determining the likelihood of victimization in crime.

Among the demographic characteristics of victims of premeditated murder, the age factor occupies a special place. Age determines not only the level of social activity of the victim, but also his attitude to dangers, life experience, and behavior in conflict situations. Also, age characteristics not only indicate in which age categories the risk of becoming a victim is high or low, but also determine the victim's life experience, attitude towards safety, and the likelihood of encountering a crime. The conducted analyses show that the majority of victims of premeditated murder belong to the working-age and socially active age categories.

Based on the above data, the following age groups were identified as victims of premeditated murder in the analyzed cases:

In particular, based on the research materials, the age structure of victims was distributed as follows: children and adolescents (under 14 years old) - 3%, young people aged 15-24 years - 12%, 25-34 years - 17%, 35-44 years - 31%, 45-54 years - 21%, 55-64 years - 11%, 65 years and older - 5%.

Analysis of these data shows that the largest number of victims of premeditated murder are persons aged 35-44 years (31%). During this age period, individuals are usually engaged in social and family responsibilities, and are at the highest stage of work activity. Therefore, they are more likely to be at the center of conflicts at work, in the family, or in personal relationships. Additionally, since individuals at this age are more socially interacting, they may be more likely to be involved as victims.

The second largest category is those aged 45-54, whose share is 21 percent. This category is also active in social and family relations. In many cases, people of this age can become victims as a result of such factors as family conflicts, property disputes, disagreements at work.

In third place are young adults aged 25-34 (17 percent), who also actively participate in social relations and sometimes become victims as a result of insufficient attention to safety requirements.

Also, the proportion of young people aged 15-24 is quite high - 12 percent. People of this age are often inexperienced, impulsive decision-makers, sometimes influenced by the opposite environment. The possibility of their becoming victims of crime is explained by this.

In the analysis, children (3%) and the elderly (5%) accounted for a smaller proportion. This situation is naturally explained by the low active social role of categories of this age in society, the low probability of direct confrontation with criminals. At the same time, cases where children and the elderly become victims of crime are associated with victimological factors such as vulnerability and vulnerability. That is, such individuals can be perceived as easy targets for criminals.

It is noteworthy that about 80% of victims belong to the category of working-age people (25-54 years old), which requires working with this age group of the population in victimological prevention, developing targeted psychosocial measures and crime protection mechanisms for them.

Analysis of the age structure of victims of premeditated murder in 2020-2024 shows that crimes are most often committed against persons of working and socially active age (25-54 years) - they constitute 69% of the total number of victims. This tendency means that crimes arise mainly in situations related to personal, domestic, or business relationships.

At the same time, vulnerable groups, such as children and the elderly (3 and 5 percent), are also identified as victims, which indicates the need to further strengthen the mechanisms for protecting these groups. This analysis substantiates the importance of developing targeted preventive measures, taking into account the distribution of crimes by age groups.

The demographic and social characteristics of victims of premeditated murder play an important role in analyzing the probability of committing premeditated murder and its social consequences. As the analysis showed, the largest number of victims are able-bodied and socially active individuals aged 25-54 years (65-70 percent), who are more likely to become victims in cases related to active participation in social relations, more frequent encounters with family and business conflicts, as well as a high level of personal life and social activity.

In addition to age, the personal characteristics of victims of crime - gender, social status, level of education, and family environment - also determine the likelihood of victimization. For example, in cases related to family conflicts and gender roles, women are more likely to become victims, while children and the elderly need social protection and can be viewed as easy targets. Young people (15-24 years old), who are inexperienced and make impulsive decisions, are also at high risk.

Studies show that the main part of crimes occurs within the framework of personal, family, or business relations. This indicates the importance of implementing targeted preventive measures in crime prevention. Psycho-sociological measures, elimination of family conflicts, conducting targeted preventive work with socially active segments of the population, as well as strengthening the mechanisms for protecting vulnerable and socially vulnerable groups will be effective in crime prevention.

At the same time, victimological analysis also shows the indirect or direct influence of victims on the crime, which serves as a scientific basis for predicting and preventing premeditated murders. Without taking into account the social and personal characteristics of

the victims, their age group and social status, it is impossible to develop effective preventive measures. Therefore, the early identification of individuals with a high degree of victimization, the introduction of psychological and social preventive measures, and the protection of vulnerable groups are of great importance in crime prevention.

In general, based on victimological data on victims of premeditated murder, the importance of developing targeted, socially and demographically justified measures and protection mechanisms in prevention and ensuring public safety is confirmed

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